

**Modeling the First, Second, and Other Waves of the Coronavirus
Outbreak (Period One, Two, and Beyond):
A Phase Space and Statistical Distribution Signal-Noise Approach to
Visualizing and Monitoring Pandemics**

Dr. Joseph Molitoris, Ph.D.

mhmolitor@aol.com, West Long Branch, NJ 07764

Professor of Physics (RET.) and Former Fellow of the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation (ITP, FIAS, University of Frankfurt, Frankfurt, Germany) and Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN, Catania, Italy)

Summary

The history and practice of statistics has long been influenced by disease and mortality accounting. The coronavirus outbreak allows for several modeling approaches. Simple models reproduce fairly well the case numbers of the coronavirus pandemic in specific regions. An extended model that includes recovery and death also reproduces the death case numbers. These models may further be used to predict future cases and updated as data becomes available in a region (city, state, country). Since the models are not complicated, they can be used by decision makers to guide their way through the exigencies of this or other pandemics. The models can be run in real time by an analyst to guide the decisions of government officials. Data is shown and compared favorably to the models for numerous states, countries, and the world. Statistical

distributions such as lognormal, Weibull, and normal can also be used to fit and model the data; we mostly use the lognormal. Correlations of data and model are typically 99.6 to 99.9 percent. Fluctuations are included with a noise and harmonics model. Our approach to modeling the coronavirus and other pandemics using a lognormal solution to the differential equations plus noise and primary harmonics is seen to work very well cross the entire spectrum of infection from lowest to highest mortalities. This self-consistent novel phase space approach allows tracking of the pandemic towards its peak and then mathematical extinction.

Introduction

The coronavirus outbreak allows for a number of possible applications to teaching [1] as well as student and faculty research [2]. In probability or statistics courses [3,4], modeling and simulation are important topics. In political science and government, data and models can also be used by decision makers to guide their way through the exigencies of this or other pandemics. In terms of psychology and politics, decisions about social distancing, travel restrictions, and the imminent opening of states and countries for normal business are influenced by both actual data [5-8] and models [1]. The cost and benefits of lock downs must also be considered.

Models and Simulations

A basic time stepped simulation [1] can be used to describe the data in a region (city, state, or country). As with the simple logistic equation, there are two parameters S and r . S the “susceptibles” is the long term population that becomes infected; r is the growth rate or transmission coefficient. The differential equation that the computer simulation solves is: $dy/dt = r y (1-y/S)$. The precision of the simulation can be verified by comparison to both analytic exponential growth and logistic model growth, respectively. With a time step of 0.1 day in the simulation, the percent error versus the logistic equation is typically less than 0.1 %.; in all the calculations shown here 0.01 day is used [1,10].

To include death and recovery requires a bit more sophistication in the model. The single differential equation is changed to a coupled set of four equations [1,9] which we have here

reduced to three:

$$(1) \frac{dy}{dt} = r y (1 - y/S - R/S - D/S) - c y$$

$$(2) \frac{dx}{dt} = -r y (1 - y/S - R/S - D/S)$$

$$(3) \frac{dz}{dt} = c y$$

where $z = R+D$ and $c = b+d$ in the more usual set of four equations [1,10]. Note that y is the number of Infected, x is the number of Susceptibles, R is the Recovered, and D is the Deaths.

Note also that since $x + y + R + D = S$ a constant, the sum of the above differential equations is zero. The parameters c , r , and S must be extracted from experimental data of the pandemic and can be adapted to the situation as the disease spreads. The initial conditions that permit the solution of the differential equations using a fixed time step procedure are that at $t = 0$, we have $y = 1$, $R = D = 0$, and $x = S-1$. The basics of this type of modeling were developed over 100 years ago [9] and are still in use today in a variety of contexts. We have extended this so-called SIR or susceptibles, infected, recovered model to a family of models that includes it as only the first approximation [10].

The cumulative number of cases $Y=y+R+D$ follows a similar set of coupled equations. A function which fits the coronavirus case and death data fairly well is the hyperbolic tangent: $Y = 1/2 S (1 + \tanh r(x-m))$. This is not surprising since under certain conditions the hyperbolic tangent and logistic function are equivalent. We program the simulation in Mathematica [11].

These type of models are adaptive in the sense that as the pandemic spreads, the model results improve in accordance with new baseline data. The data used in this paper is as of the end of September / middle of October 2020. Over nine months of data are available.

Visualization

Another way of interpreting the data or model of the pandemic in a region is via phase space.

Looking at the coupled differential equation model, all of the quantities y , D , R , x as well as their derivatives may exhibit interesting behaviour. Plots of new cases versus new deaths give useful information [1,10]. In the simplest one loop or one bump case, the orbit in phase space is a closed curve that looks roughly similar to an ellipse [1,10]. These orbits in phase space define the scope of the pandemic and allow visualization of both disease spread as well as progress towards the end of the event. Unfortunately, not all of the variables may be readily available in reported statistics and there is both errors and noise in the data. Systematic errors which result in non-trivial corrections up or down of the data are particularly troubling.

Since the total number of cases (cumulative) as well as the number of new cases (differential) - and the corresponding death data - are readily available, we plot and model new deaths versus new cases. This novel visualization technique allows for a better understanding of the evolution of the pandemic in a region.

This type of phase space region display further allows for the possible near containment of the data into a phase space area where the path to mathematical extinction (pandemic end) can be

better seen. The new case and death data, however, can be somewhat noisy due to small numbers, fluctuations, and reporting issues. In order to improve that data for visualization purposes, a smoothing over several days may be used. Further, the new case and new death data can each be modeled by a statistical lognormal distribution (the “signal”) with the addition of noise and harmonics.

Statistical Distributions

Since the number of confirmed cases for a pandemic reaches a maximum as the disease runs its course in a region, pretty much any of the probability distributions from mathematical statistics [3,4] may be used to model or fit the data. The cumulative number of cases Y equals S times the cumulative density function (c.d.f.). The rate of change dY/dt equals S times the probability density function (p.d.f.). In the case of more than one bump, we sum over values of $S \cdot \text{p.d.f.}$ for each of the bumps. The three coupled differential equations now are:

$$(4) \quad dY/dt = r(t) = S * \text{p.d.f.}$$

$$(5) \quad dx/dt = -r(t)$$

$$(6) \quad dz/dt = c y.$$

Note that $Y = y + z$. These equations may be solved using a time stepped method as used above.

Alternatively, the statistical distribution may be fit to the data and an integrating factor used to numerically determine $z=R+D$. Once z is known, R may be found by subtraction using the lognormal or another model for D . Noise (using a Gaussian or other model) and harmonics (from looking at the FFT or power spectra of the data) are easily added [1,10].

Models and Data

In most of our plots we have thus also included noise (using a Gaussian model) and harmonics (from looking at the FFT or power spectra of the data) using only the lowest three components [1,10]. For the new case data of the state of New Jersey, we show the noise data compared to our noise model in Figure 1. The data noise is in blue and the noise model in red. The main difference between the two figures is that the harmonics are not included in the model for this plot. The harmonics supplement the noise and represent periodic fluctuations.

Figures 2a and 2b show the new case data from France early on with one bump and then later as the second bump has developed. Figures 2c and 2d show data from the USA as a whole and then also the state of Louisiana. Figure 2e shows Japan with another established two bump structure plus indications of an emerging third bump. The model compares well to the data in all the cases.

A novel way of visualizing the data is in the new deaths / new cases phase space [1,10]. Figure 3a shows New York City and Figure 3b displays Louisiana in phase space. Figure 3c shows Brazil and Figure 3d gives Japan. Figure 3e shows South Korea. Figure 4a gives Germany, Figure 4b Italy, Figure 4c USA, and Figure 4d the World. Figure 4e shows data and simulation for the state of Georgia. All of these plots are in the new deaths / new cases phase space. Note the variety of forms! Note also the emerging second and third bumps in both Figures 2abcde and some of these.

In order to focus on the topology that is most clear in the model without noise and harmonics, we show the underlying lognormal functional models for new cases and new deaths (respectively) plotted in phase space. Figure 5a shows New York State, 5b Louisiana, 5c the USA, and 5d the World. Note in particular the two roughly elliptical shapes for Louisiana. The two bumps in the lognormal representation, the model with noise and harmonics, and the data all have these shapes (for Louisiana) which correspond to different flow angles: roughly one (1.0) vs. two (2.2) degrees. Figure 5e for Japan is a somewhat different two loop structure than that of Louisiana; the same is true for Figure 5f of South Korea. The coronavirus thus maps out these different curves in phase space similar to what happens with a pendulum making Lissajous figures in the sand [1].

Time Dependent Measures: Flow Angle and Path Length

In the case of one loop (such as Figure 5a with New York state), a Death Flow Angle is easily extracted from the data or model [10]. With more than one loop, the flow angle is roughly the average of those from the multiple loops. For the case of Louisiana (Figures 2c, 3b and 5b), we thus end up with a 1.3 degree flow angle at the end in both the data (1.36) and the model (1.31).

Either matrix diagonalization or a simple linear fit produce the same result for the flow angle [1].

Since this angle directly relates to the mortality, as the phase space distribution evolves it too varies with time. Early on the mortality tends to be greater so that the angle peaks at mid-course and may then saturate at the end of the pandemic in a region. See Figures 6abcdef.

Figure 6a shows Pennsylvania, New Jersey, and New York State flow angle evolution. Figure 6b gives the results for Georgia, Florida, and Louisiana. Figure 6c shows France, Italy, and Germany. Figure 6d is of India, USA, and Brazil. Figure 6e compares three USA regions: Michigan, Texas, and California. Figure 6f compares three countries: China, Japan, and South Korea. Figure 7 plots the flow angle versus the mortality for over twenty regions of the World. Our approach to modeling the coronavirus and other pandemics using a lognormal solution to the differential equations plus noise and primary harmonics is seen to work very well cross the entire spectrum of infection from lowest to highest mortalities.

The path length of the loop in phase space is also a good measure of the pandemic. Figure 8a shows the time evolution of this path length for Michigan and Figure 8b gives the result for Florida. Figure 8c is of the USA and Figure 8d is for Mexico. Note that both with the five day data smoothing and without it the model and data agree very well in these and other cases.

Figures 9abc show the final path length values for over twenty regions (as of September/October 2020) plotted versus the number of confirmed cases. In all of these regions, the model and data agree well and the result may be parameterized with a simple logarithmic fit.

Figure 10abcd displays most of the model variables (cases, deaths, infected, recovered) versus time for Germany, Pennsylvania, Italy, and France. This more traditional type of plot is well known from the literature [1,10,12].

Figure 11abc gives the power spectrum of the new deaths variable for Florida, New Jersey, and Brazil. Figure 11d gives the power spectrum for new cases in Mexico. The first few harmonics are very clear in both data and model in most cases. Sometimes, the noise or issues with the data will overshadow the harmonics. Similarly, Figures 12a and 12b give a spectrogram for the new deaths data and model for Louisiana. Figures 13a and 13b give the spectrogram for Germany. The spectrogram plots the magnitude of the discrete Fourier transforms of the partitions of the data [11]. It can supplement the power spectrum plots.

Noise

The noise has a critical role in both the simulation and in reality. Some of the orbits in smaller loops will not happen or get washed out when the noise is significant. Further, the transition from a metastable to either a growing or decaying viral population is noise related. Each of the bumps or waves of the new cases thus begins as a fluctuation or noise. Either the fluctuation grows or is damped out. The signal thus depends intimately on the noise. Figure 1 displayed the noise data and model for New Jersey. Figures 14abc shows the variation of the noise with the magnitude of the signal (new cases or new deaths) again for over twenty regions of the world. Sometimes the data will have more (or less) noise than expected from this parameterization. Further, the harmonics can also have a significant effect in many cases. There is an interplay between the harmonics and the noise in determining the power spectrum, which is nearly featureless without those elements. Our approach complements other techniques which use chaos theory [13].

Conclusions

Figure 15 is our concluding figure and shows the evolution of the virus in France, the United Kingdom, and the United States of America over almost nine months. Though the coronavirus was especially deadly in certain regions (e.g. Wuhan, New York City, London, and France) for a few weeks time, over the course of the year the mortality has waned. The case numbers may have grown with better and wider testing, but the survival rate has increased dramatically even in vulnerable populations such as the aged. In a testament to both human durability and the power of modern medicine, most infected people have survived to include well known personalities such as Prime Minister Johnson of the UK and President Trump of the USA.

In conclusion, we have examined a variety of mathematical approaches to modeling the coronavirus pandemic in real time as it happened. Both the time stepped simulation and probability density function approaches reproduce the data fairly well and allow decision makers to plan in accordance with the progress of the pandemic [12] from inception to end. This self-consistent novel phase space approach allows tracking of the pandemic towards its peak and then mathematical extinction. Our approach to modeling the coronavirus and other pandemics using a lognormal solution to the differential equations plus noise and primary harmonics is seen to work very well cross the entire spectrum of infection from lowest to highest mortalities [10].

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Figure 1. New Jersey data compared to the simulation. For the new cases data of the state of New Jersey, we show the noise data compared to our noise model.

Figure 2. New cases time evolution for the simulation and data.

Figures 2a and 2b show the data from France early on with one bump and then later as the second bump has developed.

New Cases

Data

Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)

Figure 2b. France.

New Cases

— Data

— Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)

Figure 2c. Louisiana.

New Cases

— Data

— Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)

Day

Figure 2d. USA.

New Cases

— Data

— Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)

Day

Figure 2e. Japan.

New Cases

Figure 3. A phase space approach to the simulation and data.

Figure 3a shows New York City.

Figure 3b displays Louisiana in phase space.

New Deaths

— Data

— Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)

— Model (Lognormal D.E.)

New Cases

Figure 3c displays Brazil in phase space.

Figure 3d displays Japan in phase space.

Figure 3e gives South Korea in phase space.

Figure 4a gives Germany data vs. simulation.

New Deaths

- Data
- Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)
- Model (Lognormal D.E.)

Figure 4b Italy.

New Deaths

- Data
- Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)
- Model (Lognormal D.E.)

New Cases

Figure 4c USA.

New Deaths

- Data
- Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)
- Model (Lognormal D.E.)

Figure 4d. World.

New Deaths

- Data
- Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)
- Model (Lognormal D.E.)

Figure 4e. The USA state of Georgia.

New Deaths

- Data
- Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)
- Model (Lognormal D.E.)

Figure 5. A phase space approach to the simulation and data. Lognormal functionals are shown.

Figure 5a shows New York State.

New Deaths

— Model (Lognormal D.E.)

Figure 5b. Louisiana.

New Deaths

New Cases

— Model (Lognormal D.E.)

Figure 5c. USA.

New Deaths

— Model (Lognormal D.E.)

Figure 5d. World.

New Deaths

— Model (Lognormal D.E.)

Figure 5e. Japan.

New Deaths

— Model (Lognormal D.E.)

Figure 5f. South Korea.

New Deaths

— Model (Lognormal D.E.)

New Cases

Figure 6abcd. Flow angle data compared to the simulation.

Figure 6a shows Pennsylvania, New Jersey, and New York State flow angle evolution.

Death Flow Angle (deg)

New Jersey Data

Model

New York Data

Model

Pennsylvania Data

Model

Day

Figure 6b gives the results for Georgia, Florida, and Louisiana.

Death Flow Angle (deg)

● Louisiana Data

● Model

● Georgia Data

● Model

● Florida Data

● Model

Figure 6c shows France, Italy, and Germany.

Death Flow Angle (deg)

● France Data

● Model

● Italy Data

● Model

● Germany Data

● Model

Figure 6d is of India, USA, and Brazil.

Death Flow Angle (deg)

India Data

Model

USA Data

Model

Brazil Data

Model

Day

Figure 6e compares three USA states: Michigan, Texas, and California.

Death Flow Angle (deg)

● Michigan Data

● Model

● Texas Data

● Model

● California Data

● Model

Day

Figure 6f compares three countries: China, Japan, and South Korea.

Death Flow Angle (deg)

- Japan Data
- Model
- China Data
- Model
- South Korea Data
- Model

Figure 7 plots the flow angle versus the mortality for over twenty regions of the World.

Death Flow Angle (deg)

Figure 8. Path length data versus the model.

Figure 8a shows the time evolution of this path length for Michigan.

Figure 8b gives the result for Florida.

Path Length

- Data Unsmoothed
- Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)
- Data Smoothed
- Model Smoothed

Figure 8c is of the USA.

Path Length

- Data Unsmoothed
- Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)
- Data Smoothed
- Model Smoothed

Figure 8d is for Mexico.

Path Length

- Data Unsmoothed
- Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)
- Data Smoothed
- Model Smoothed

Figures 9 abc show the final path length values for over twenty regions (as of September 2020) plotted versus the number of confirmed cases.

Figure 9a. Lowest scale.

Figure 9b. Intermediate scale.

Figure 9c. Highest scale.

Figure 10abcd displays most of the model variables (cases, deaths, infected, recovered) versus time for Germany, Pennsylvania, Italy, and France.

Figure 10a. Germany.

Figure 10b. Pennsylvania.

Figure 10c. Italy.

Figure 10d. France.

Figure 11ab gives the power spectrum of the new deaths variable for Florida and New Jersey.

Figure 11a. Florida.

Figure 11b. New Jersey.

Figure 11c gives the power spectrum of the new deaths variable for Brazil.

Figure 11d gives the power spectrum for new cases in Mexico.

Figures 12a and 12b give a spectrogram for the new deaths data and model for Louisiana.

Figure 12a. Data.

Figure 12b. Model. Spectrogram for the new deaths variable in the model for Louisiana.

Figures 13a and 13b give the spectrogram for Germany.

Figure 13a. Data.

Figure 13b. Model. Spectrogram for Germany.

Figures 14abc shows the variation of the noise with the magnitude of the signal (new cases or new deaths).

Figure 14a. Lowest scale.

Noise

● Data

— Model

Figure 14b. Intermediate scale.

Figure 14c. Highest scale.

Figure 15 is our concluding figure and shows the evolution of the virus in France, the United Kingdom, and the United States of America over almost nine months.

Death Flow Angle (deg)

● France Data

● Model

● United Kingdom Data

● Model

● USA Data

● Model

Day